

CULTURAL SHOCK AS A SOCIAL ISSUES

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This article is devoted to the problems that people face when they go to foreign countries in adapting to the customs and traditions of that country, getting to know and making friends with people there.

Key words.

social, honeymoon, distress, orientation, adaptation, traditions, new environment.

Culture shock refers to the impact of moving from a familiar culture to one that is unfamiliar. This impact includes the anxiety and feelings (such as surprise, disorientation, uncertainty, and confusion) felt when a person must adapt to a different and unknown cultural or social environment. It might include the shock of a new environment, meeting new people, eating new food, or adapting to a foreign language, as well as the shock of being separated from the important people in your life: such as family, friends, colleagues, and teachers.

Culture shock generally comes in four stages. These stages are:

1. The Honeymoon Stage
2. The Distress Stage
3. The Orientation Stage
4. The Adaptation Stage

The Honeymoon Stage During this stage, everything is new and interesting. You may experience a feeling of euphoria and be in awe of all the differences you see and experience. You feel excited and stimulated, and you still feel close to everything familiar back home. During this stage, you generally focus on the similarities between your home country and your host country, but you appreciate the differences as well.

The Distress Stage Once the honeymoon stage wears off, you may suddenly start getting frustrated or annoyed by your new country, specifically the customs and values. The things you're experiencing no longer feel new; in fact, it's starting to feel like the strangeness of a new culture is preventing you from experiencing things. You may feel hostility toward the way things are done here, and you may

think that they should be done in a different way. You start to idealize life “back home,” and may feel that your current culture, language, and food are inferior to what you're used to. You feel confused and alone, and may realize that the familiar support systems of home are no longer easily accessible to you. Don't worry; this is perfectly normal.

The Orientation Stage The Orientation Stage is the first stage in acceptance. During this stage, you begin to understand why things are done in a certain way. You start to respect the culture and traditions, whether you consider them to be good or bad. You begin to feel more comfortable in your new environment, and you begin to have a more positive outlook. You feel more confident and better prepared to cope with any problems that might arise. Remember that culture shock is not a perfectly linear experience; you may return to the Distress Stage multiple times until you hit...

The Adaptation Stage During this stage, your attitude changes and you are able to function in both cultures. You have embraced the new culture and are able to see it in a new, yet realistic, light. In this stage you are typically well-oriented to your new life, and have developed your own habits and routines. You feel comfortable, confident, and capable of making decisions. You no longer feel alone and isolated; instead, you start to feel at home.

Factors that can contribute to culture shock

Climate Many students find the northwest climate can affect them a lot. You may find the grayness and dampness, especially during the winter months, difficult to get used to.

Language Listening and speaking in a new language is tiring. In class, some international students have trouble understanding the lecture and reading materials. People speak quickly and you may feel embarrassed to ask them to repeat what they said. If English is not your first language, you may find you miss your home language.

Social roles Social behaviors may confuse, surprise or offend you. For example you may find people appear cold, distant or always in a hurry. Or you may be surprised to see couples holding hands and kissing in public. You may find the relationships between men and women more formal or less formal than you are used to, as well as differences in same sex social contact and relationships.

'Rules' of behavior As well as the obvious things that hit you immediately when you arrive, such as sights, sounds, smells and tastes, every culture has unspoken rules which affect the way people treat each other. These may be less obvious, but sooner or later you will probably encounter them and once again the

effect may be disorientating. For example, there will be differences in the ways people decide what is important, how tasks are allocated and how time is observed. In business and academic life, keeping to a schedule is important. You should always be on time for lectures, classes, and meetings with academic and administrative staff. If you are going to be late for a meeting, do try to give advance notice.

Values Although you may first become aware of cultural differences in your physical environment, (e.g. food, dress, behavior) you may also come to notice that people from other cultures may have very different views of the world from yours. Cultures are built on deeply-embedded sets of values, norms, assumptions and beliefs. It can be surprising and sometimes distressing to find that people do not share some of your most deeply held ideas, as most of us take our core values and beliefs for granted and assume they are universally held. As much as possible, try to suspend judgment until you understand how parts of a culture fit together into a coherent whole. Try to see what people say or do in the context of their own culture's norms. This will help you to understand how other people see your behavior, as well as how to understand theirs. When you understand both cultures, you will probably find some aspects of each that you like and others that you don't.

Relationship Stress If your spouse or partner has accompanied you to the U.S., remember that the stress of the transition may cause struggles in your relationship. The transition to a new culture may be very difficult for your partner. Your partner may feel very isolated; he/she has been transplanted from your culture and separated from family and friends. Simple tasks can be stressful due to the language barrier. Often times they do not have opportunities to engage in productive, meaningful activity such as pursuing a degree, and it may be more difficult for them to make new friends.

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